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Review of Aerodynamic, Euler, Flight Path, and Principal Angles Used in Flight Mechanics Applications

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15. Abstract This technical note provides a somewhat detailed review of the aerodynamic, Euler, flight path, and principal angles used in flight mechanics applications. It explores their significance, mathematical formulations, and relationships, focusing on their applications in aerospace engineering. Some disputed angles are clarified in the light of primary sources. The American nomenclature is matched with the equivalents of German notation; hence, a small contribution to the literature has been made. The information presented here is also useful for conceptual fixed-wing aircraft design studies and represents the adopted notations by the author for further improvements on ADA.	
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Foreword

This report represents the compilation of aerodynamic, Euler, flight path, and principal angles that find use in flight mechanics applications. The information presented herein is useful for conceptual and preliminary fixed-wing aircraft design studies. The main objective of the report is, as much as possible, to fix the notations for the angles as mentioned earlier. To substantiate the angle notations, primary sources were referenced, and corresponding illustrations were incorporated.

The contributions of Arda Çalışkan (Turkish Aerospace, Flight Mechanics Chief Engineer, M.S. TU Delft - Aerospace Eng.) and Abdulkерim Aksakal (Turkish Aerospace, Senior Flight Mechanics Engineer, B.Eng. University of Queensland - Aerospace Eng.) as critics are gratefully acknowledged.

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List of Symbols

Latin	Description
C_{x_y}	Nondimensional stability derivative (e.g., C_{L_α} , C_{n_β} , etc.)
n_y	Lateral load factor
n_z	Vertical load factor (usually abbreviated as n)
O	Origin of a reference frame and its axes (e.g., $Ox_e y_e z_e$ or simply O_e)
p, q, r	Body axes angular velocity components about x_b , y_b , and z_b
u, v, w	Body axes translational velocity components along x_b , y_b , and z_b
V	Wind axes total velocity ($V = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2 + w^2}$)

Greek	Description
α	Angle of attack
β	Sideslip angle
γ	Flight path elevation angle
ϵ	Angle of nose-up
η	Angle of attack of x_p -axis
θ	Pitch angle
μ	Flight path bank angle
π	Used to denote angles in radians (e.g., $\pi/2$ rad = 90 deg)
σ	Flight path heading angle (per Kalviste)
ϕ	Roll angle
χ	Flight path heading angle (per other scholars)
ψ	Yaw angle

Introduction

In flight mechanics applications, some angles are taken for granted. However, they are rarely totally comprehended. To establish a solid background in flight mechanics, engineers must know the definitions and formulations of those angles. In this regard, the esteemed paper of Kalviste opens with the following sentence [1]:

“In order to analyze aircraft maneuvers, the engineer must know the aircraft attitude, flight path direction, and aircraft attitude relative to the flight path.”

This technical note discusses all kinds of angles that find use in flight mechanics applications. It does so, with the subsections of:

- **Definition**
- **Formulation**
- **Notes**

In the “Definition” subsections, the associated angle is discussed and defined in light of the sources. If there appears to be a conflict between the definitions, the commonly accepted definition is adopted. In the “Formulation” subsections, the associated angle is, if possible, definitively formulated; if not possible, the angle is formulated relating to the other angles used in flight mechanics. If the equation is of high importance, such that it defines the angle, it is boxed. In the “Notes” subsections, some observations about the angles, either by the scholars or the author, are noted. Throughout the report, the phrases “the author” or “this author” refer to the one who wrote this report. Other authors are referred to by name.

This technical note marks the beginning of the ADA - Flight Mechanics Investigation Series. Under this series, it is aimed to document various flight mechanics topics under distinct headings for further improvements to ADA.

1 Aerodynamic Angles

In flight mechanics applications of fixed-wing aircraft (e.g., fighter, attack, cargo, airliner, UAV, etc.), there are only two aerodynamic angles: α and β . The aircraft flow angles (angle of attack and sideslip) define the relation between the wind and the body axes systems [2].

The comparison of body, stability, and wind axes is then quite essential in understanding the aerodynamic angle concepts. These are, unfortunately, given in textbooks with low resolution, and most of them are confusing. Thereupon, the author prepared Figure 1.1 so that the relationships between the velocities and angles are all clear with one illustration.

Figure 1.1: Visualization of Aerodynamic Angles

With the aerodynamic angle concepts, the relationship between the velocity vector, hence total speed of the aircraft, V , and rectangular components of the velocity in body-axis, i.e. u , v , and w , is established as:

$$u = V \cos \beta \cos \alpha \quad (1.1)$$

$$v = V \sin \beta \quad (1.2)$$

$$w = V \cos \beta \sin \alpha \quad (1.3)$$

$$V = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2 + w^2} \quad (1.4)$$

Before investigating the aerodynamic angles, it is better to understand the body-fixed planes of the aircraft. These are illustrated in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2: Body Axes Planes of Aircraft

$x_b z_b$ -plane: is the symmetry plane, dividing the aircraft into left and right halves; it runs from the tail to the nose, and is perpendicular to y_b -axis. Thus, it forms the vertical-longitudinal plane. The motion involved around this plane is the rotation about the y_b axis, and is called “pitch”. If the $x_b z_b$ -plane is a true symmetry plane, i.e., left and right halves of the aircraft are mirror images (aircraft is not loaded with asymmetric external stores!), then the products of inertia I_{xy} and I_{yz} are zero.

$y_b z_b$ -plane: divides the aircraft into front and rear halves; it runs from wingtip to wingtip, or it is parallel to the vertical plane that runs through wingtip to wingtip and beyond, and is perpendicular to the x_b -axis. Thus, it forms the vertical-lateral plane. The motion involved around this plane is the rotation about the x_b -axis, and is called “roll”.

$x_b y_b$ -plane: divides the top and bottom halves of the aircraft horizontally; it is perpendicular to the z_b -axis. Thus, it forms the transverse (or horizontal) plane. The motion involved around this plane is the rotation about the z_b -axis, and is called “yaw”.

1.1 α , Angle of Attack

1.1.1 Definition

Wright [3]: α is angle of attack, angle between the projection of the wind x-axis (x_w) on the xz-plane and the body x-axis (x_b); positive rotates the +z-axis into the +x-axis.

Kalviste [1]: α is the angle of attack, the angle between the aircraft x-axis and the projection of the velocity vector on the aircraft xz-plane; positive rotation is from the z-axis toward the x-axis.

Hence, it is understood that the angle of attack is the angle between the body x-axis and the vector that is obtained by projecting the local air velocity vector onto the symmetry plane, $x_b z_b$ -plane (See Figure 1.2) of the aircraft.

1.1.2 Formulation

The definitive formulation of the angle of attack can be established from Figure 1.1 as:

$$\boxed{\alpha = \arctan\left(\frac{w}{u}\right)} \quad (1.5)$$

or

$$\boxed{\alpha = \arcsin\left(\frac{w}{\sqrt{u^2 + w^2}}\right)} \quad (1.6)$$

The angular range of α is given by Etkin [4] as:

$$-\pi \leq \alpha \leq \pi \quad (1.7)$$

Diston [5], on the other hand, gives the following angular range for α :

$$-\pi < \alpha \leq \pi \quad (1.8)$$

According to Kalviste [1], α can be formulated using the Euler and flight path angles as either:

$$\boxed{\alpha = \arcsin\left\{\frac{\cos \gamma[\sin \theta \cos \phi \cos(\chi - \psi) - \sin \phi \sin(\chi - \psi)] - \sin \gamma[\cos \theta \cos \phi]}{\cos \beta}\right\}} \quad (1.9)$$

or

$$\boxed{\alpha = \arccos\left\{\frac{\cos \gamma[\cos \theta \cos(\chi - \psi)] + \sin \gamma[\sin \theta]}{\cos \beta}\right\}} \quad (1.10)$$

1.1.3 Notes

- Note that the Equations 1.9 and 1.10 are not the definitions of the angle of attack but useful relationships relating α to Euler and flight path angles.
- Among the possible definitions of the angle of attack, the one given in Equation 1.5 is mostly used.
- There are only three stability derivatives that includes α in the longitudinal dynamics of the aircraft: $C_{L\alpha}$, $C_{D\alpha}$, and $C_{m\alpha}$. There are also angle of attack rate derivatives: $C_{L\dot{\alpha}}$, $C_{D\dot{\alpha}}$, and $C_{m\dot{\alpha}}$.
- Two stability derivatives involving α are primary design parameters: $C_{L\alpha}$ and $C_{m\alpha}$.
- The angle of attack of a planform is arbitrarily defined as the angle of attack of its root chord [6].
- The angle of attack at which the aircraft stalls is called “stall angle of attack”. However, the “cobra maneuver” of the Su-27 has previously demonstrated post-stall maneuvering of fighter jets.
- From the point of view of aircraft performance, a higher angle of attack means a lower speed in a level flight [7].
- Even in formal texts, the angle of attack is abbreviated as AoA.
- The British call it the “Angle of Incidence”.
- The Germans call it “(der) Anstellwinkel”.
- In Turkish, it is called “hücum açısı”, a literal translation of the original naming [8].

1.2 β , Sideslip Angle

1.2.1 Definition

Wright [3]: β is the angle of sideslip in the stability axis system, angle between the wind x-axis (x_w) and the projection of this axis on the xz-plane; positive rotates y_s -axis into the x_s -axis.

Kalviste [1]: β is the sideslip angle, the angle between the velocity vector and the aircraft xz-plane; positive direction is when the velocity vector is to the right of the xz-plane, when looking forward.

Kundu [9]: By definition, the angle of sideslip, β , is positive when the free-stream velocity vector, V , relative to the aircraft is from the right (i.e., the aircraft nose is to the left of the velocity).

Schmidt [10]: The sideslip angle β lies in the $x_s y_s$ -plane, and is the angle between V (velocity vector) and x_s -axis.

Occasionally, the sideslip angle is also called the “angle of sideslip” and usually abbreviated as AoS.

1.2.2 Formulation

The definitive formulation of the sideslip angle is either:

$$\boxed{\beta = \arcsin\left(\frac{v}{V}\right)} \quad (1.11)$$

or

$$\boxed{\beta = \arctan\left(\frac{v}{\sqrt{u^2 + w^2}}\right)} \quad (1.12)$$

from Figure 1.1. The angular range of β is given by Etkin [4] as:

$$-\pi \leq \beta \leq \pi \quad (1.13)$$

Diston [5], on the other hand, gives the following angular range for β :

$$-\pi/2 \leq \beta \leq \pi/2 \quad (1.14)$$

The sideslip angle can also be formulated regarding Euler and flight path angles as given by Kalviste [1]:

$$\boxed{\beta = \arcsin\{\cos \gamma[\sin \theta \sin \phi \cos(\chi - \psi) + \cos \phi \sin(\chi - \psi)] - \sin \gamma \cos \theta \sin \phi\}} \quad (1.15)$$

1.2.3 Notes

- Note that Equation 1.15 is not the definitive formulation of β ; rather, it shows the relationship between β and other angles that is being described in this report.
- There are only three stability derivatives that includes β in the lateral-directional dynamics of the aircraft: C_{n_β} , C_{l_β} , and C_{y_β} . There are also sideslip angle rate derivatives: $C_{n_{\dot{\beta}}}$, $C_{l_{\dot{\beta}}}$, and $C_{y_{\dot{\beta}}}$.
- Two stability derivatives involving β are primary design parameters: C_{n_β} and C_{l_β} .
- The local angle of sideslip is less than the freestream sideslip angle because of a “side-wash” effect largely due to the fuselage [11].
- Pitch, roll, and yaw control effectiveness degrade as sideslip is increased. The reasons are that symmetric pitch and roll control surfaces become asymmetric with sideslip, thereby creating reduced forces and moments. Sideslip creates sidewash, which can affect pitch, roll, and yaw forces, but in particular yaw. As sideslip increases, symmetric aircraft become less and less streamlined, inducing difficult-to-predict nonlinear flow effects [12].
- In an aircraft turning maneuver with an extreme sideslip angle, the loss of sufficient airflow may cause the engine to shut down [13].
- Unlike the common misconception, the sideslip angle need not be zero during a coordinated turn. In fact, in a coordinated turn, either the sideslip angle, β , or lateral load factor, n_y , is zero.
- For any sideslip angle, the drag force is increased and the forward speed is reduced [13].
- Sideslip generates both the yawing and rolling moments that lead to a coupled motion between β , ψ , and ϕ . For this reason, the lateral motion is always coupled with the directional, and together they are called lateral-directional dynamics of the aircraft.
- Large sideslip angles are undesirable for several important reasons. The effectiveness of the aerodynamic control surfaces may be greatly reduced, and directional stability may be lost. Even if the directional stability is maintained, a large side force can be developed that may break the vertical tail [14].
- When the motion involves β , it is categorized as “asymmetric flight”.
- Some texts denote the sideslip angle as the Greek letter σ . This notation, however, is long considered obsolete. It can be found in the work of Miele [15].
- In German, the sideslip angle is called “(der) Schiebewinkel”. In Turkish, it is called “yan(a) kayma açısı” [8], which is a literal translation of the original naming.

2 Euler Angles

It is known that the angular position of the aircraft may be described by three Euler angles (or by four quaternions (also called “Euler parameters” [16]), or nine direction cosines) [17]. These angles define the attitude of the aircraft in space and are designated by the Greek letters: ψ , θ , and ϕ .

Wright [3]: ψ , θ , and ϕ constitute a system of three angles which uniquely defines the orientation of the body-axes system with respect to a fixed reference set of axes. Any orientation of the body axes system is obtained by rotating the reference axes system through each of the three angles in turn. The sequence in which these orientations are taken is important. If the sequence is changed, the orientation of the body axes system with respect to the fixed reference set of axes will change.

The definitions of Euler angles, like flight path angles, are a bit trickier than those of other angles due to intermediate axes. These are better explained in Figures 2.1 and 2.2.

Figure 2.1: Visualization of Euler Angles

Note. Reprinted from Brockhaus [18]

The German notations used for axes and their American equivalents are given in Table A.1.

Figure 2.2: Representation of Euler Angles

Note. Reprinted from Diston [19]

When orienting from a fixed frame of reference, say NED (or Earth-fixed frame) to body axes system, the accepted convention of sequence of rotations in aerospace engineering is fixed as $3 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 1$, which correspond to a rotation sequence of $\psi \rightarrow \theta \rightarrow \phi$, respectively. Thus, a rotation by angle ψ about z_e -axis, followed by a rotation by θ about the intermediate y -axis, and finally a rotation by ϕ about x_b -axis (see [20, p. 44]) one transports the O_e to the O_b with no change in the alignment to the CG of the aircraft.

Durham states that the principal range of values of the Euler angles is fixed largely by convention and may vary according to the application [16]. However, every other scholar uses a different range as shown in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Adopted Range of Euler Angles by Scholars

Durham [16]	Diston [5]	Stevens et al. [14]	Allerton [21]
$0 \leq \psi < 2\pi$	$0 \leq \psi < 2\pi$	$-\pi < \psi \leq \pi$	$-\pi \leq \psi \leq \pi$
$-\pi/2 \leq \theta \leq \pi/2$			
$-\pi \leq \phi < \pi$	$-\pi < \phi \leq \pi$	$-\pi < \phi \leq \pi$	$-\pi \leq \phi \leq \pi$

It is observed that an agreement between scholars is not found on the accepted range of Euler angles, though each one of them puts the pitch angle, θ , in the same range.

2.1 ψ , Yaw Angle

2.1.1 Definition

Kalviste [1]: ψ is the aircraft heading angle, horizontal angle between some reference direction (e.g., north) and the projection of the aircraft x-axis on the horizontal plane; positive rotation is from north to east.

Wright [3]: ψ is the angle of yaw, positive rotates the +x-axis into the +y-axis.

2.1.2 Formulation

Per Kalviste [1], ψ can be formulated in conjunction with χ as either:

$$\sin(\psi - \chi) = \left\{ \frac{\sin \alpha \sin \mu - \cos \alpha \cos \mu \sin \beta}{\cos \theta} \right\} \quad (2.1)$$

or

$$\cos(\psi - \chi) = \left\{ \frac{-\sin \alpha \sin \gamma \cos \mu + \cos \alpha \cos \gamma \cos \beta - \cos \alpha \cos \gamma \sin \mu \sin \beta}{\cos \theta} \right\} \quad (2.2)$$

Since the values inside the parentheses on the left-hand side of the above formulations can be of either sign, it is better to leave them as they are.

2.1.3 Notes

- Euler angle rates establish a relationship with the body angular velocities of p , q , and r . $\dot{\psi}$ is related to angular velocities and other Euler angles as:

$$\dot{\psi} = \sec \theta (q \sin \phi + r \cos \phi) \quad (2.3)$$

- In German, heading angle is called either “(der) Steuerkurs” or “(der) Gierwinkel”.

2.2 θ , Pitch Angle

2.2.1 Definition

Wright [3]: θ is the angle of pitch, positive rotates +z-axis into the +x-axis.

Kalviste [1]: θ is the aircraft pitch angle, vertical angle between the aircraft x-axis and the horizontal plane; positive rotation is up.

2.2.2 Formulation

Per Kalviste [1], θ can be formulated using aerodynamic, Euler, and flight path angles as:

$$\theta = \arcsin\{(\sin \alpha \cos \gamma \cos \mu) + (\cos \alpha \sin \gamma) \cos \beta + (\cos \alpha \cos \gamma \sin \mu) \sin \beta\} \quad (2.4)$$

The reader will remember that the classical texts mostly present the pitch angle, θ , as:

$$\theta = \alpha + \gamma \quad (2.5)$$

without clearly stating the conditions. However, the derivation of Equation 2.5 follows from Equation 2.4. Assume, β and μ are both absent, i.e., zero. This idealization is in fact possible! In other words, motion is pure longitudinal. Then, Equation 2.4 reduces to:

$$\theta = \arcsin\{(\sin \alpha \cos \gamma) + (\cos \alpha \sin \gamma)\} \quad (2.6)$$

It is seen that the right-hand side parenthesis represents the trigonometric sum of $\sin(\alpha + \gamma)$, hence:

$$\theta = \arcsin\{\sin(\alpha + \gamma)\} \quad (2.7)$$

Cancelling the inverse functions, we are left with the most common formulation of θ :

$$\theta = \alpha + \gamma \quad (\text{assuming } \beta = \mu = 0.) \quad (2.8)$$

under the assumption of $\beta = \mu = 0$, i.e., the flight is symmetric (longitudinal motion only).

2.2.3 Notes

- Euler angle rates establish a relationship with the body angular velocities of p , q , and r . $\dot{\theta}$ is related to angular velocities and other Euler angles as:

$$\dot{\theta} = q \cos \phi - r \sin \phi \quad (2.9)$$

- In German, pitch angle is either called “(die) Längsneigung” or “(der) Nickwinkel”.

2.3 ϕ , Roll Angle

2.3.1 Definition

Wright [3]: ϕ is the angle of roll, positive rotates the +y-axis into the +z-axis.

Kalviste [1]: ϕ is the aircraft roll angle, the angle between the aircraft xz-plane and the vertical plane containing the aircraft x-axis; positive rotation is clockwise, about the x-axis, looking forward.

2.3.2 Formulation

Per Kalviste [1], ϕ can be formulated using aerodynamic, Euler, and flight path angles as:

$$\phi = \arcsin \left\{ \frac{\cos \gamma \sin \mu \cos \beta - \sin \gamma \sin \beta}{\cos \theta} \right\} \quad (2.10)$$

or

$$\phi = \arccos \left\{ \frac{\cos \alpha \sin \gamma \cos \mu - \sin \alpha \sin \gamma \cos \beta - \sin \alpha \cos \gamma \sin \mu \sin \beta}{\cos \theta} \right\} \quad (2.11)$$

2.3.3 Notes

- Euler angle rates establish a relationship with the body angular velocities of p , q , and r . $\dot{\phi}$ is related to angular velocities and other Euler angles as:

$$\dot{\phi} = p + \tan \theta (q \sin \phi + r \cos \phi) \quad (2.12)$$

- For a small value of angle of attack, the roll angle ϕ and the bank angle μ are approximately equal [1].
- In German, roll angle is either called “(der) Hängewinkel” or “(der) Rollwinkel”.

3 Flight Path Angles

There are three flight path angles, which are denoted as χ , γ , and μ . In German notation (See Table A.1), the flight path angles are visualized in Figures 3.1 and 3.2.

Figure 3.1: Representation of χ and γ

Note. Reprinted from Brockhaus [18]

Figure 3.2: Representation of χ , γ , and μ

Note. Reprinted from Brockhaus [18]

3.1 χ , Flight Path Heading Angle

3.1.1 Definition

Kalviste [1]: χ is the flight path heading angle, horizontal angle between some reference direction (e.g., north) and the projection of the velocity vector on the horizontal plane; positive rotation is from north to east.

3.1.2 Formulation

Per Kalviste [1], χ can be formulated in conjunction with ψ as either:

$$\sin(\chi - \psi) = \left\{ \frac{\cos \phi \sin \beta - \sin \phi \sin \alpha \cos \beta}{\cos \gamma} \right\} \quad (3.1)$$

or

$$\cos(\chi - \psi) = \left\{ \frac{[\cos \alpha \cos \theta + \sin \alpha \sin \theta \cos \phi] \cos \beta + \sin \theta \sin \phi \sin \beta}{\cos \gamma} \right\} \quad (3.2)$$

Since the values inside the parentheses on the left-hand side of the above formulations can be of either sign, it is better to leave them as they are.

3.1.3 Notes

- Note the notational difference: This angle is denoted in the United States (Stengel, Zipfel, Miele, and others) and Germany (Brockhaus) as χ ; however, Kalviste denoted this angle with σ while giving its relationship-based formulation. Complying with the rest of the world, the letter χ is adopted in this study.
- Stengel [20] names this angle as the “horizontal flight path angle”.
- Miele [15] calls this angle the “velocity yaw”.
- Boiffier [22] refers to this angle as the “aerodynamic azimuth angle”.
- Diston [5] calls this angle the “track angle” and gives the range $0 \leq \chi < 2\pi$.
- When there is no wind and $\phi = \beta = 0$, i.e., motion is pure longitudinal, it is deduced that $\chi = \psi$; also, $\gamma = \theta - \alpha$. Equations 3.1 and 3.2 can be used as checks. Under the same conditions, the flight path axes coincide with both the wind and stability axes.
- For crabbing flight, χ is equal to ψ , since the maneuver sets the trim at $\phi = \beta = 0$.
- For an SHSS (steady heading sideslip) maneuver, upon entering ψ and β as inputs, the computed parameter χ must satisfy Equations 3.1 and 3.2.

3.2 γ , Flight Path Elevation Angle

3.2.1 Definition

Kalviste [1]: γ is the flight path elevation angle, vertical angle between the velocity vector and the horizontal plane; positive rotation is up.

3.2.2 Formulation

Per Kalviste [1], γ is formulated as:

$$\boxed{\gamma = \arcsin\{(\sin \theta \cos \alpha - \cos \theta \cos \phi \sin \alpha) \cos \beta - \cos \theta \sin \phi \sin \beta\}} \quad (3.3)$$

In classical textbooks, the γ is usually defined as:

$$\gamma = \theta - \alpha \quad (3.4)$$

Without clearly stating the conditions. However, the derivation of Equation 3.4 follows from Equation 3.3. Assume, β and ϕ are both absent, i.e., zero. Then the equation reduces to:

$$\gamma = \arcsin\{(\sin \theta \cos \alpha - \cos \theta \sin \alpha)\} \quad (3.5)$$

Taking the sine of two sides yields:

$$\sin \gamma = (\sin \theta \cos \alpha - \cos \theta \sin \alpha) \quad (3.6)$$

The right-hand side of the equation is simply the trigonometric difference of $\sin(\theta - \alpha)$, hence:

$$\sin \gamma = \sin(\theta - \alpha) \quad (3.7)$$

Taking the inverse sine of both sides yields the most common formulation of γ :

$$\boxed{\gamma = \theta - \alpha \quad (\text{assuming } \beta = \phi = 0.)} \quad (3.8)$$

3.2.3 Notes

- The flight path elevation angle is commonly referred to as flight path angle in the academic community and sometimes abbreviated as FPA.
- Zipfel [23] notes that to initialize 6-DoF simulations, it is most convenient to use the Euler angles ψ , θ , ϕ , and the incidence angles α , β . Given these angles, derive the equations that determine the flight-path angles χ and γ .
- Stengel [20] refers to this angle as the “vertical flight path angle”.

- Miele [15] refers to this angle as the “velocity pitch”.
- Boiffier [22] refers to this angle as the “aerodynamic climb angle”.
- Diston [5] refers to this angle as the “climb/dive angle” and gives the following range:
 $-\pi/2 \leq \gamma \leq \pi/2$.
- The use of γ gives the sense of either leveling, climbing, or descending with respect to the horizontal plane.
- The definition of flight path angle, γ , resulted in “Flight-Path Stability” requirement in MIL-F-8785 and its successor MIL-STD-1797.
- In a 6-DoF trim code, while performing a coordinated turn maneuver, upon entering the throttle setting, roll angle, and n_y , the output γ should be the same as the Equation 3.3 suggests.

3.3 μ , Flight Path Bank Angle

3.3.1 Definition

Kalviste [1]: μ is the flight path bank angle, the angle between the plane formed by the velocity vector and the lift vector, and the vertical plane containing the velocity vector; positive rotation is clockwise, about the velocity vector, looking forward.

Stengel [20]: In typical flight conditions, the bank angle (μ) is very nearly the same as the roll angle (ϕ). However, the former is measured about the velocity vector while the latter is measured about the body x-axis. In a steady horizontal turn, the bank angle, μ , is approximately equal to the roll angle, ϕ .

Per Stengel, the angle μ is between the velocity and wind axes as shown in Figure 3.3.

3.3.2 Formulation

The flight path bank angle, or in short: bank angle, μ , is formulated as a relationship using aerodynamic, Euler, and flight path elevation angle by Kalviste [1] as:

$$\mu = \arcsin \left\{ \frac{\cos \theta \sin \phi \cos \beta + (\cos \alpha \sin \theta - \sin \alpha \cos \theta \cos \phi) \sin \beta}{\cos \gamma} \right\} \quad (3.9)$$

or

$$\mu = \arccos \left\{ \frac{\cos \alpha \cos \theta \cos \phi + \sin \alpha \sin \theta}{\cos \gamma} \right\} \quad (3.10)$$

The question that must be raised at this point is the definition of vertical load factor, n_z . A survey leads to Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Definition of Vertical Load Factor, n_z , per Scholars

Scholar	Formula	Notes from Scholars
Sadraey [24]	$n = 1/\cos \phi$	“Load factor is only a function of the bank angle.”
Raymer [11]	$n = 1/\cos \phi$	“n due to a bank angle ϕ is obtained from this eq.”
Yechout [25]	$n = 1/\cos \phi$	“Defines the rel. between n and ϕ for a level turn.”
Roskam [6]	$n = 1/\cos \phi$	“The concept of load factor is $L = nW$.”
Schmidt [26]	$n = 1/\cos \phi$	“A steady turn with $\phi = 60$ deg induces $n = 2$.”
Phillips [27]	$n = \cos \gamma / \cos \phi$	“General rel. for n in a steady climbing or diving turn.”
Durham [16]	$n \approx \sec \phi$	“Rel. between n and bank angle (many assumptions).”
Pamadi [28]	$n = 1/\cos \mu$	“Load factor in turn.”
Stengel [20]	$\mu = \arccos (1/n)$	“The steady-state bank angle can be expressed as”
Hull [29]	$\cos \mu = 1/n$	“ $0 = L \cos \mu - W$ can be solved for the bank angle as”

The reader of this report will notice that the roll angle ϕ is not the same as the flight path bank angle μ . So, why this much confusion? First of all, the correct naming for n_z should be “vertical load factor” so that the distinction between n_z and n_y is made clear, where the latter must be named as the “lateral load factor”. The key to understanding the concept of vertical load factor is hidden in the note given in the parentheses by Durham, meaning that the formulations given by scholars are not “entire equations” but rather “meaningful approximations”. However, anyone who has ever performed 6-DoF trim analyses of coordinated turn maneuvers realized that this “meaningful approximation ($n_z = 1/\cos\phi$)” does not work if the analysis includes γ , i.e., the aircraft might be climbing or descending during the turn. Therefore, the formulations of Pamadi and Stengel should be adopted for the vertical load factor to cover all three types of turn coordination maneuvers: (i) level coordinated turn ($\gamma = 0$), (ii) climbing turn ($\gamma > 0$), (iii) descending turn ($\gamma < 0$). Since the formulation itself is not an “equation” but rather an “approximation” to the analytical solution of vertical load factor, it should be written as $n_z \approx 1/\cos\mu$. Now, the angle μ can either be taken from Equation 3.9 or 3.10, depending on the nature of the turn maneuver in question.

If the coordinated turn maneuver, regardless of sign and value of γ , is forced with $\beta = 0$ (i.e., freeze β to zero), and hence a small n_y (i.e., float n_y) is permitted, the approximation for the vertical load factor should be formulated as:

$$\boxed{n_z \approx \frac{1}{\cos\mu} = \frac{\cos\gamma}{\cos\alpha \cos\theta \cos\phi + \sin\alpha \sin\theta}} \quad (3.11)$$

whereas, if the turn maneuver, regardless of sign and value of γ , is forced with $n_y = 0$ (i.e., freeze n_y to zero), and hence a small β (i.e., float β) is permitted, the approximation for the vertical load factor should be formulated as:

$$\boxed{n_z \approx \frac{1}{\cos\mu} = \frac{1}{\cos \left\{ \arcsin \left[\frac{\cos\theta \sin\phi \cos\beta + (\cos\alpha \sin\theta - \sin\alpha \cos\theta \cos\phi) \sin\beta}{\cos\gamma} \right] \right\}}} \quad (3.12)$$

This author suggests that the coordinated turn maneuvers be performed and analyzed with $n_y = 0$ while permitting a small β , and note that the Equations 3.11 and 3.12 are not found in any textbook. What these equations describe is that when an aircraft is performing a climbing turn, n_z will be less than it ought to be with the same ϕ in a level coordinated turn. The inverse is also true: when an aircraft is performing a descending turn, n_z will be greater than it ought to be with the same ϕ in a level coordinated turn. The terms “fixed”, “float”, and “freeze” as used in trim studies can be found in the paper of Millidere et al. [30] with many maneuver examples.

Figure 3.3: Relationship between Velocity and Wind Axes

Note. Reprinted from Stengel [20]

To exemplify the significance of the above discussions, three examples are generated for a conceptual fifth-generation fighter jet in ADA as follows.

Example 1: A conceptual fifth-generation fighter jet is performing a climbing turn at 5000 ft flying at Mach 0.6 with fixed values of $\phi = 60$ deg and $\gamma = 12$ deg. The trim is established at $\alpha = 3.502$ deg, $\beta = -0.020477$ deg, and the pitch angle is computed as $\theta = 13.9923$ deg. Then, by Equation 3.12, the aircraft is pulling approximately 1.9563 g's.

Example 2: Same fighter jet is performing a descending turn at 10,000 ft flying at Mach 0.75 with fixed values of $\phi = 60$ deg and $\gamma = -15$ deg. The trim is established at $\alpha = 2.5065$ deg, $\beta = -0.0012478$ deg, and the pitch angle is computed as $\theta = -13.3538$ deg. Then, by Equation 3.12, the aircraft is pulling approximately 2.0454 g's.

Example 3: Same fighter jet is performing a level coordinated turn at 5000 ft flying at Mach 0.6 with fixed values of $\phi = 60$ deg and $\gamma = 0$ deg. The trim is established at $\alpha = 3.5892$ deg, $\beta = -0.017157$ deg, and the pitch angle is computed as $\theta = 2.0604$ deg. Then, by Equation 3.12, the aircraft is pulling approximately 1.9961 g's.

3.3.3 Notes

- The flight path bank angle, μ , must not be confused with the roll angle, ϕ .
- Miele [15] refers to this angle as the “velocity roll”.
- Boiffier [22] refers to this angle as the “aerodynamic bank angle”.
- Diston [5] refers to this angle as the “bank angle” and gives the range $-\pi < \mu \leq \pi$.
- Notice, how the velocity axes becomes the wind axes if the former is positively rotated by $+\mu$ around the velocity vector. Rotate Figure 3.1 about the velocity vector by $+\mu$ and the wind axes in Figure 3.2 is obtained ($y_k \rightarrow y_a$ in German notation; $y_v \rightarrow y_w$ in American notation). This is also equivalent to the definition of Stengel.
- Since the lift vector is always perpendicular to the velocity vector, the bank angle is the measure of lift vector rotation [1].
- Flight path bank angle μ is defined about the velocity vector. Hence, the transformation between the velocity and wind axes is done only with this angle. A rotation of $+\mu$ rotates the axes from the velocity to the wind, as the right-hand rule suggests. See Figure 3.3.
- The corrected approximation (too good for any phase in aircraft design, less than $\pm 3\%$ error compared to 6-DoF trim) for vertical load factor, n_z , should be formulated as $n_z \approx 1/\cos \mu$, and Equations 3.11 and 3.12 can be used depending on the nature of the turn maneuver as described previously.

4 Principal Angles

Principal angles derive from the definition of the principal axes, and they are denoted as ϵ and η . However, they are hardly ever used in modern flight mechanics applications. They become handy only in axes transformations, and hence, in inertia.

4.1 ϵ , Angle of Nose-up

4.1.1 Definition

The angle ϵ is defined by different scholars as follows:

Abzug [31]: ϵ is the angle of nose-up incidence of fuselage reference line relative to x_p -axis. (By fuselage reference line, Abzug clearly refers to x_b -axis. See Figure 4.3.)

Thelander [32]: The angle ϵ denotes the angle between the principal axis, x_p , and the body x-axis, x_b .

Chodoba [12]: The angle ϵ denotes the angle between the principal axis x_p and the body x-axis. (See Figure 4.2)

Wolowicz [33]: ϵ is the angle between body x-axis and principal x-axis; positive when reference is above principal axis at the nose. (See Figure 4.5.)

Etkin et al. [34]: ϵ is the angle between x_p (principal axis) and x_s (stability axis), positive as shown in Figure 4.1. (This definition corresponds to the definition of angle η .)

Figure 4.1: Wrong Representation of Principal Axis and ϵ

Note. Reprinted from Etkin et al. [34], they confused ϵ with η and x_s with x_p .

Figure 4.2: Representation of Principal Axis and ϵ

Note. Reprinted from Chudoba [12]

4.1.2 Formulation

By Campbell et al. [35] and Thelander [32], the definitive formulation of ϵ is given as:

$$\boxed{\epsilon = \alpha - \eta} \quad (4.1)$$

4.1.3 Notes

- Principal axes are defined by the condition [32]: $I_{xy_p} = I_{yz_p} = I_{xz_p} = 0$.
- Chudoba's choice of the Greek letter for "epsilon" (ϵ) is used interchangeably instead of ϵ and might be confusing. The correct typography is ϵ (lunate epsilon, math variant used in aerospace engineering, also used to denote the downwash angle in aerodynamics).
- In general, no range has been given for principal angles. In nominal flight conditions, they are relatively small. However, one can foresee that, as α increases due to flight conditions, ϵ should stay about the same while η must increase by $\alpha_2 - \alpha_1$ in order to satisfy Equation 4.1. Say, two different flight conditions are established in point 1 and 2 in time with: $\eta_1 = \alpha_1 - \epsilon_1$; $\eta_2 = \alpha_2 - \epsilon_2$. Also, assume that between the flight conditions 1 and 2, the mass moments of inertia I_{xx} , I_{zz} , and the product of inertia I_{xz} about the body x-axis are essentially the same, i.e., fuel burn is negligible, which signifies a time delay of less than a minute for most aircraft, i.e., $t_2 - t_1 < 60$ seconds, because $\epsilon = (1/2) \arctan\{2I_{xz}/(I_{zz} - I_{xx})\}$, a formulation for the inclination of the principal axis, is well established. Thus, $\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_2 \Rightarrow \Delta(\eta) = \eta_2 - \eta_1 = \alpha_2 - \alpha_1$. If the time elapsed between point 1 and 2 is significant, then the ϵ should be computed by the inclination formula, and the resultant η should be found by $\eta = \alpha - \epsilon$.

4.2 η , Angle of Attack of x_p -axis

4.2.1 Definition

Abzug [31]: η is the angle of attack of the x_p -axis. (The reason Abzug names this angle as the AoA of x_p -axis must have been due to an analogy in the definition of α , See Figure 4.3.)

Figure 4.3: Relation of Angle of Attack and Principal Axes Angles

Note. Reprinted from Abzug [31]

Campbell et al. [35]: η is the angle between principal longitudinal axis of inertia and longitudinal body axis. (See Figure 4.4)

Figure 4.4: System of Axes and Angular Relationships in Flight

Note. Reprinted from Campbell et al. [35]

Wolowicz [33]: η is the angle of inclination of principal x-axis relative to stability x-axis; positive when principal x-axis is above stability x-axis at the nose.

Figure 4.5: Body, Stability, Principal, and Wind Axes

Note. Reprinted from Wolowicz [33], subscript “o” denotes the principal axes.

4.2.2 Formulation

Thelander [32] and Campbell et al. [35] give the definitive formulation of angle η , whereas Abzug shows it without writing it down in Figure 4.3, and Wolowicz also shows the relationship in Figure 4.5. Hence, the definitive formulation of η is given in Equation 4.2 as (also from Equation 4.1):

$$\boxed{\eta = \alpha - \epsilon} \quad (4.2)$$

4.2.3 Notes

- The stability and principal axes differ by the angle η .
- In British nomenclature, the Greek letter η corresponds to elevator deflection (e.g., δ_η) which must not be confused with the angle η of principal axes.

Summary

In summary, the angles that find use in flight mechanics applications can be collectively presented as in Table 4.1 in the order of appearance in this report.

Table 4.1: Collection of Angles Used in Flight Mechanics

Adopted Full Name	Sym.	Defined	Category	Formulation (Definitive and/or Relationship)
Angle of Attack	α	Btw. x_s and x_b	Aerodynamic	$\alpha = \arctan(w/u)$ or $\alpha = \arccos\{[\cos \gamma \cos \theta \cos(\chi - \psi) + \sin \gamma \sin \theta]/\cos \beta\}$
Sideslip Angle	β	Btw. x_w and x_s	Aerodynamic	$\beta = \arcsin(v/V)$ or $\beta = \arctan(v/\sqrt{w^2 + u^2})$ or $\beta = \arcsin\{\cos \gamma [\sin \theta \sin \phi \cos(\chi - \psi) + \cos \phi \sin(\chi - \psi)] - \sin \gamma \cos \theta \sin \phi\}$
Yaw Angle	ψ	See Fig. 2.1 and 2.2	Euler	$\sin(\psi - \chi) = \{[\sin \alpha \sin \mu - \cos \alpha \cos \mu \sin \beta]/\cos \theta\}$ or $\cos(\psi - \chi) = \{-\sin \alpha \sin \gamma \cos \mu + \cos \alpha \cos \gamma \cos \beta - \cos \alpha \cos \gamma \sin \mu \sin \beta\}/\cos \theta\}$
Pitch Angle	θ	See Fig. 2.1 and 2.2	Euler	$\theta = \arcsin\{(\sin \alpha \cos \gamma \cos \mu) + (\cos \alpha \sin \gamma) \cos \beta + (\cos \alpha \cos \gamma \sin \mu) \sin \beta\}$
Roll Angle	ϕ	See Fig. 2.1 and 2.2	Euler	$\phi = \arcsin\{[\cos \gamma \sin \mu \cos \beta - \sin \gamma \sin \beta]/\cos \theta\}$ or $\phi = \arccos\{[\cos \alpha \sin \gamma \cos \mu - \sin \alpha \sin \gamma \cos \beta - \sin \alpha \cos \gamma \sin \mu \sin \beta]/\cos \theta\}$
Flight Path Heading Angle	χ	Btw. true north and the projection of the velocity vector on the horizontal plane	Flight Path	$\sin(\chi - \psi) = \{[\cos \phi \sin \beta - \sin \phi \sin \alpha \cos \beta]/\cos \gamma\}$ or $\cos(\chi - \psi) = \{[(\cos \alpha \cos \theta + \sin \alpha \sin \theta \cos \phi) \cos \beta + \sin \theta \sin \phi \sin \beta]/\cos \gamma\}$
Flight Path Elevation Angle	γ	Btw. velocity vector and the horizontal plane	Flight Path	$\gamma = \arcsin\{(\sin \theta \cos \alpha - \cos \theta \cos \phi \sin \alpha) \cos \beta - \cos \theta \sin \phi \sin \beta\}$
Flight Path Bank Angle	μ	About velocity vector	Flight Path	$\mu = \arcsin\{[\cos \theta \sin \phi \cos \beta + (\cos \alpha \sin \theta - \sin \alpha \cos \theta \cos \phi) \sin \beta]/\cos \gamma\}$ or $\mu = \arccos\{[\cos \alpha \cos \theta \cos \phi + \sin \alpha \sin \theta]/\cos \gamma\}$
Angle of Nose-up	ϵ	Btw. x_p and x_b	Principal	$\epsilon = \alpha - \eta$
Angle of Attack of x_p -axis	η	Btw. x_p and x_s	Principal	$\eta = \alpha - \epsilon$

There are also longitude (λ) and latitude (φ) angles, but they are not as common as the ones presented above, and they do not mean much in the trim analysis and preliminary design work; rather, they are used to position the aircraft on the surface of the Earth. Also note that the relationships written for ϕ can also be organized for θ .

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Appendices

A Comparison of Reference Frames between the U.S. and DE

The reference frames and the associated coordinate systems can be confusing in aerospace engineering. Every other author invents their specific notation; hence, an agreement is not met in the naming of reference frames and coordinate systems (See Table B.1). However, Table A.1 is prepared to clear the frames and axes used in Germany and their American equivalents, since this technical note involves illustrations with German notations. In the following table, the American notation was based on the works of Stengel and Beeker, whereas the German equivalents are based on the works of Brockhaus and Klußmann et al [36].

Table A.1: Equivalent Reference Frames between the American and German Notation

American (per Stengel & Beeker)		German (per Brockhaus & Klußmann et al.)	
Reference Frame	Axes	Reference Frame	Axes
Inertial	$Ox_i y_i z_i$	Inertial	$Ox_i y_i z_i$
Geocentric (ECEF)	$Ox_{ec} y_{ec} z_{ec}$	Geozentrisch (Erdfest)	$Ox_e y_e z_e$
Earth-Fixed (Earth/NED)	$Ox_e y_e z_e$	Erdlotfest (Geodätisch)	$Ox_g y_g z_g$
Air-Trajectory (Wind)	$Ox_w y_w z_w$	Flugwindfest (Aerodynamisch)	$Ox_a y_a z_a$
Flight Path (Velocity)	$Ox_v y_v z_v$	Flugbahnfest (Kinematisch)	$Ox_k y_k z_k$
Body-Fixed (Body)	$Ox_b y_b z_b$	Körperfest (Flugzeugfest)	$Ox_f y_f z_f$
Body-Fixed (Stability)	$Ox_s y_s z_s$	Körperfest (Experimentell)	$Ox_e y_e z_e$
Propulsion (Thrust)	$Ox_t y_t z_t$	Triebwerk (Schub)	$Ox_s y_s z_s$

The body, stability, and wind axes are represented in German notation as in Figure A.1.

Figure A.1: Representation of Body, Stability and Wind Axes

Note. Reprinted from Brockhaus [18]

B Reference Frames & Axes per Scholars

In modern applications of flight mechanics analyses, it has been observed that every author of a new thesis or book adopts one or a combination of the reference frames and axes compiled in Table B.1 to initiate their analyses, meaning that an agreement on the reference frames and associated axes is not met. The adopted reference frames and their interrelationships are the subject of a separate report.

Table B.1: Naming of the Reference Frames and Associated Axes per Scholars

Scholar	No. of Axes	List of Frames and/or Axes Mentioned
Miele (1962, [15])	4	(i) Ground Axes System, (ii) Local Horizon System, (iii) Wind Axes System, (iv) Body Axes System
Thelander (1965, [32])	8	(i) Earth Axes, (ii) Body Axes, (iii) Stability Axes, (iv) Principal Axes, (v) General Wind Axes, (vi) Symmetric Wind Axes, (vii) Wind-Tunnel Stability Axes, (viii) Nonrolling Axes
Edwards AFB (1968, [37])	7	(i) Inertial Coordinate System, Earth Axes: (ii) Fixed Earth Axes, (iii) Moving Earth Axis; Body Axis Systems: (iv) General Body Axis System, (v) Stability Axis System, (vi) Principal Axis System, (vii) Wind Axis System
Etkin (1972, [4])	7	(i) Inertial Reference Frame (Inertial Axes), (ii) Earth-Fixed Reference Frame (Earth Axes), (iii) Vehicle-Carried Vertical Frame, (iv) Atmosphere-Fixed Reference Frame, (v) Air-Trajectory Reference Frame (Wind Axes), (vi) Body-Fixed Reference Frame (Body Axes), (vii) Stability Axes
McLean (1990, [38])	5	(i) Earth Axes, (ii) Body-Fixed Axes, (iii) Stability Axes, (iv) Principal Axes, (v) Wind Axes
Beeker (1993, [39])	8	(i) Inertial, (ii) Flat Earth Referenced, (iii) Inertial Navigation Unit, (iv) Body-Fixed, (v) Stability, (vi) Wind, (vii) Flight Path, (viii) Thrust
Boiffier (1998, [22])	6	(i) Inertial Frame, (ii) Normal Earth-Fixed Frame, (iii) Vehicle-Carried Normal Earth Frame, (iv) Body Frame, (v) Aerodynamic or Air-Path Frame, (vi) Kinematic or Flight-Path Frame
Zipfel (2000, [23])	7	(i) Heliocentric Frame (Heliocentric and inertial coordinate systems), (ii) Geocentric-Inertial (J2000) Frame (Geographic coordinate system), (iii) Earth Frame (Earth coordinate system), (iv) Body Frame (Body coordinate system), (v) Wind coordinate systems, (vi) Flight-path coordinate system, (vii) Local-level coordinate system (NED)
Pamadi (2004, [28])	6	(i) Inertial Axes System, (ii) Earth-Fixed Axis System (ECEF), (iii) Navigational System, Body Axes Systems: (iv) Body Axes System, (v) Stability Axes System, (vi) Wind Axes System
Stengel (2004, [20])	8	(i) Inertial Reference Frame, (ii) Geocentric Frame (ECEF), (iii) Earth-Fixed Geographic Frame (NED), (iv) Body-Axis, (v) Stability-Axis, (vi) Principal-Axis, (vii) Wind-Axis, (viii) Velocity-Axis
Durham (2013, [16])	9	(i) Inertial Reference Frame, (ii) Earth-Centered Reference Frame, (iii) Earth-Fixed Reference Frame, (iv) Local-Horizontal Reference Frame, Body-Fixed Reference Frames: (v) Principal Axes, (vi) Zero-Lift Body-Axis System, (vii) Stability-Axis System; (viii) Wind-Axis System, (ix) Atmospheric Reference Frame